

Engineering Cellular Caspsases to induce apoptosis upon infection by Polyprotein-encoding viruses by hijacking the proteolytic activity of viral proteases.

Daoyu Zhang

Abstract

Many highly pathogenic viruses encodes polyproteins and a protease that processes such polyprotein into functional protein subunits, which is necessary for the replication or the assembly of said viruses.

Caspases are cellular enzymes that induce apoptosis of the cell upon activation by proteolytic cleavage of a linker sequence between the mature protein subunits of the enzyme.

As viruses require a living cell to replicate and assemble, the specific induction of apoptosis of infected cells has been demonstrated in the past to be a highly effective antiviral strategy both In Vitro and In Vivo [1].

In this proposal, we performs a literature review on the viral families that encodes polyproteins and proteases, past experimental evidence of Apoptosis-induction based antiviral strategies involving both natural and designed mechanisms, and propose an universal strategy of long-lasting, mutation- and escape- resistant antiviral protection both as a prophylactic and as a therapeutic.

Polyprotein-and-protease-encoding Viruses

Most viruses belonging to the order Ortervirales (except for Caulimoviridae) and Pisuviricota (except for Duplopiviricetes), with the addition of Togaviridae and Flaviviridae encodes a conserved Protease to process their polyproteins into functional protein subunits. This protease is unique to each virus Family and their activity is not found in an uninfected cell. The viral Protease is ubiquitous to ssRNA(+) virus Biology and is indispensable for the replication and assembly of most ssRNA(+) and all ssRNA reverse-transcribing viruses.

Due to the presence of multiple protease cleavage sites within such viral polyproteins, the cut site sequence of viral proteases are highly conserved within each Genus, and the cost of it's mutational escape is extremely high, primarily due to the presence of multiple such sites within these viral polyproteins requiring all the protease cleavage sites and the protease active site itself to change simultaneously for the resulting mutant genome to remain functional and viable.

A literature review revealed the genomic arrangement, protease location and cut sites for typical ssRNA positive stranded and ssRNA reverse transcribing viruses.

Figure 2 from Rodamilans, Shan et al[2] Showing Plant viruses from representative genera that encodes polyproteins and corresponding Proteases.

A Branch 2: "Picornavirus supergroup" (1901)

B

Figure 3 from Wolf, Kazlauskas et al. [3] Showing representative families of ssRNA positive-stranded viruses from the phylum Pisuviricota and their Proteases.

A Branch 3 (1,208)

B

Figure 4 from Wolf, Kazlauskas et al. [3] Showing representative families of ssRNA positive-stranded viruses from the phylum Kitrinoviricota and their Proteases.

Figure.1: Flaviviridae Polyprotein showing NS3 Protease cut sites [4].

Figure.2: Picornaviridae Polyprotein showing 3C protease cut sites [4].

Figure.3: Astroviridae Genome with ORF1ab polyprotein processed by a Protease domain encoded by the ORF1a protein Nsp1a [4].

Figure 2A from Fernández-Correa, Truchado et al. Showing the location of the Astrovirus Protease within its genome[5].

Figure.4: Potyviridae polyprotein with cut site of the encoded P1-pro, HC-pro and N1a-pro Proteases[5].

Figure.5: Togaviridae genome with the non-structural Polyprotein processed by nsp2 Protease.

B

	P4	P3	P2	P1	P1'	P2'	P3'	P4'
FCV F4-1:	M	R	A	E	A	C	P	S
FCV F4-2:	F	R	S	E	D	V	A	N
FCV F4-3:	F	E	A	E	D	G	C	S
FCV F4-4:	P	K	S	E	A	K	G	K
FCV F4-5:	F	A	E	E	S	G	P	G
FCV F4-6:	F	R	L	E	A	D	D	G

Figure 1 from Yokoyama, Oka et al.[6] Showing a Calicivirus genome with sites processed by the p76 Protease.

Figure.6: Sobemoviridae genome with ORF2A and ORF2AB polyprotein processed by the Pro protease[5].

Figure.7: Barnaviridae genome with ORF2A and ORF2AB polyprotein processed by an uncharacterized protease encoded by the ORF2A protein[5].

Figure 1 from Clara, Aartjan et al.[7] Showing Genomic arrangement from representative families from order Nidvirales, their polyproteins and encoded Proteases and their putative cut sites.

Figure.8: Genomic arrangements and Protease cut sites of Alpha-,Beta-,Gamma-,Epsilon-retrovirus, Lentivirus and Spumavirus from the Family Retroviridae.[4]

Table 1: Known viral Proteases with their cleavage site consensus sequence[12]

Protease name and viral family	Consensus sequence(s) of cleavage
HIV Protease(Lentiviridae)	
HRV Protease 3C(Picornaviridae)	
Nla-Pro (Potyviridae)	
P76 (Caliciviridae)	
nsp2(Alphaviridae)	

Cellular apoptosis by the activation of Caspases

Cellular Caspases are driving force behind the highly conserved Eukaryotic process known as Apoptosis, the programmed death of cells triggered by a large variety of external and internal stimuli. As viruses require a living host cells to replicate, and viral RNA and DNA that failed to assemble into active virions are rendered inactive upon cell death, the activation of cellular apoptosis pathway upon the recognition of viral infection have long been long recognized as an efficient and escape-resistant antiviral strategy.

A literature review on the Cellular Apoptosis cascade revealed that all initiator caspases, Caspase-9, Caspase-8 and Caspase-10, require induced proximity to activate, and is not activated by the Interdomain cleavage of the procaspase interdomain linker alone. While the Effector caspase, Caspase-3, is capable of activating Caspase-6 and Caspase-7, but is incapable of activating or inducing the activation of initiator Caspases. There is not enough information to determine whether the cleavage of the Prodomains for Caspase-8 and Caspase-10 result in activation.

Figure 1 from Hanna and Wilfried[11] showing cleavage site engineering of the Human Caspase-3 (CASP3) and activation by the Human Rhinovirus-14 3C protease In-Vitro.

Figure 1 from Vocero-Akbani, Heyden et al.[9] showing the process of engineering a transducing variant of Caspase-3 for the killing of HIV-infected cells through selective proteolytic activation of apoptosis by the HIV-1 protease.

Overexpression and transduction of Procaspase-3 appears to be safe as Procaspase-3 itself does not induce apoptosis upon overexpression[16] or transduction[9].

Activation of Caspase-3 alone appears to be sufficient to induce the death of neuronal cells in *Drosophila*[10] using an engineered Caspase-3 that is activated upon exposure to light.

Fig 5 from [10] showing the rate of survival of *Drosophila* with expression of a light-activated Caspase 3 in Motor neurons.

Bid

The BH3 interacting-domain death agonist, or Bid protein, was one of the zymogens that are responsible for the initiation of the intrinsic pathway of cellular Apoptosis. During the induction of Apoptosis, an activated Caspase-8, Caspase-10 or Granzyme B[17] (from Killer T cells) cleaves Bid to form a truncated version, tBid which then interacts with BAK[18] and forms pores in the Mitochondrial outer membrane, initiating cytochrome C release from the mitochondria, depolarization of the mitochondrial inner membrane and result in the formation of the apoptosome through the binding of Cytochrome C to APAF-1, and the initiation of it's subsequent oligomerization.

Figure 3 from Fischer, Stroh et al[13] showing differential cleavage of Bid by Caspase-3, Caspase-8, Granzyme B and Caspase-10.

Upon activation, Bid is cleaved to form either a p15 fragment or a p13 fragment, both of which could then target the outer membrane of Mitochondria and initiate the release of cytochrome C from the mitochondrial intermembrane space[19].

Figure 3 from Korsmeyer, Wei et al[19] showing Bid in either the p15 form or the p13 form being able to initiate the release of Cytochrome C from the mitochondria.

Figure 1 from Riddle-Taylor, Nagasaki et al[14] showing the effect of mutation of the two cleavage sites on Bid

Bid can be safely fused to a protein transduction domain, Tat, and delivered to cancer cells, where it sensitizes cancer cells to apoptotic induction but does not significantly enhance apoptosis by itself.[15]

Figure 1 from Orzechowska, E.J. et al.[15] Specifying the format of a recombinant Bid protein with a HIV-1 Tat Protein Transduction Domain fused to the N-terminus.

Delivery through a Non-replicating Adenovirus vector of an engineered the bid protein that include a Hepatitis C virus NS3/NS4A protease cut site replacing a stretch of amino acids from the Amino Acid position 62-71, and having amino acid position D60, D75 and D98 replaced with E which abolishes cleavage by endogenous proteases, have been found to be effective in inducing the specific Apoptosis of cells infected by the Hepatitis C virus, which have been found to completely prevent the infection of a Sindbis virus model that depends on a recombinant Hepatitis C Virus NS3 protease for assembly in a Cell culture. Injection of such a vector have been found to completely clear low titers of HCV and decrease the titers of HCV by up to 10^2 to 10^3 in a Chimeric Human liver Mouse model[20].

Figure 9: The structure of Bid, showing amino acid position 62-71 that is to be substituted by a viral protease cleavage site in Cyan, and amino acid position D60, D75, D98 which are to be replaced with E in order to inactivate the native cleavage sites for Granzyme B and Caspase-8.

Figure 1 from Hsu, Hsi et al. [20] showing Modified Bid with cleavage site of the Hepatitis Virus NS3 inserted into the amino acid position 62 of the Human Bid protein, which have a highly specific Apoptosis-inducing activity (F) in cells that expresses the Hepatitis C NS4A-NS3 protease, A replicon of Hepatitis C virus, or a Sindbis virus model that depends on a recombinant Hepatitis C virus NS3 protease for assembly.

Apaf-1

The Apoptotic protease activating factor 1 protein, or APAF-1, is the center piece of the Intrinsic pathway of cellular apoptosis. In its native form, APAF-1 is autoinhibited by its own WD40 repeat domain [37], which is released upon binding to Cytochrome C and dATP, enabling the oligomerization of APAF-1 which enables the recruitment and activation of Caspase-9, initiating the intrinsic pathway of cellular apoptosis.

Interestingly, the removal of the WD-40 domain, whether through the expression of the truncated APAF-1 1-559 protein[37], or through the proteolytic processing of Apaf-1 by Caspase-3[38], causes the rest of APAF-1 to directly oligomerize, without the need for Cytochrome C. This truncated Apaf-1 oligomer is functional for recruitment and activation of procaspase-9.[37]

Figure 1 from Yuanming, Liyun et al[37] showing the recruitment and activation of procaspase-9 by truncated APAF-1 1-559

Figure 6 from Kirsten, Helga et al[38] showing the proteolytic processing site within Apaf-1 which result in the formation of an N-terminal fragment. Note that Caspase-3 also cleaves Apaf-1 at amino acid position 20, resulting in it's inactivation and release of any bound caspase-9 that were previously attached to the full-length Apaf-1-dATP-Cytochrome C complex.

Using structure-guided design, we discovered that the Caspase-3 cleavage site within the peptide 789-NLEDPQED-796 is located on an unstructured loop. This allow the substitution of the segment 791-EDP-793 with a cleavage site of a viral protease, without interfering with the folding or autoinhibition of Apaf-1. Although we did not find a publication on an in-vitro or in-vivo modification to Apaf-1 in order to booby-trap it against a viral protease, there is no structural constraint for the engineering of proteolytic activation of Apaf-1 by a heterogeneous, viral protease.

Figure 10: Structure of the Human Apoptosome showing the truncation site F559 (in Magenta) and the Caspase-3 cleavage site D796 (in Pink). Cytochrome C is shown in Yellow while Caspase-9 is shown in light blue.

Figure 11: the structure of the full-length Murine Apaf-1. F559 is in Magenta while D796 is in Pink.

Upon cleavage of Apaf-1 at the loop 789-NLEDPQED-796, the resulting fragment should be able to oligomerize in the same manner as the known p84 fragment[38], while the intact N-terminal CARD domain of the cleaved Apaf-1 should retain it's ability to recruit and activate procaspase-9, similar to the known 1-559 fragment.

Delivery of modified proteins into cells

Cell-Penetrating peptides

As there exist no method of gene delivery that can provide an 100% transfection efficiency to all cells within a living multicellular organism after the zygote stage, and due to the necessity to have 100% of the cells within a patient to contain the Protease-trapped apoptosis induction molecules in order to fully protect against viral infections, A Protein transduction domain (PTD) is necessary for the successful construction of a prophylactic and therapeutic vector targeting viral diseases using this Apoptosis-Inducing strategy when it comes to in-vivo efficacy.

HIV-1 TAT

The HIV-1 TAT peptide, GRKKRRQRRRPQ, is the most studied CPP known. It is capable of delivering functional macromolecules, including enzymes, into the cytoplasm and the delivered molecules are biologically active.[1] However, the use of the TAT peptide is plagued by it's extremely inefficient secretion due to the presence of multiple furin cleavage sites within the peptide sequence[21].

Despite recent advancements and partial success in engineering the TAT peptide to be seretable and still perform the protein transduction function In-Vitro, using modified TAT variants like the Tat-κ, YARKAARQARA [21], the lack of In-Vivo efficiency of even modified TAT remains a major challenge in designing viable cell-penetrating peptides necessary for the delivery of large, biologically active protein molecules in-vivo.

Alternatives to HIV-1 TAT that does not contain furin recognition sites yet still maintains their ability to deliver proteins into the cytoplasm of human and mammalian cells.

Table 2: List of known Protein Transduction Domains with efficacy in delivering macromolecular cargoes into the cytoplasm of cells

Name	Sequence	Evidence of delivery	Furin cleavability of peptide (Prop 1.0[22])
translationally controlled tumor protein(TCTP)-PTD	MIIYRDLISH	In-Vitro(HELA cells) with Fluorophores and in-vivo(mouse) with β-galactosidase [23]	0.108(-)
translationally controlled tumor protein(TCTP)-PTD -35	LIIFAILISHKK	In-Vitro(HELA cells) [23] [24]	0.101(-)
translationally controlled tumor protein(TCTP)-PTD -26	MIIFAIAASHKK	In-Vitro(HELA cells) [23] [24]	0.114(-)
CUPID peptide	RRVQIWFQNKRAKVKR RRVQIWFQNKRAKVKR SKGEELFTG(GFP) RRVQIWFQNKRAKVKR GGPFGKGD(XP_638704.1)	In-Vitro(multiple species) with demonstrated GFP refolding and activity[25]	0.746(+) with GFP(Aequorea Victoria) and 0.328(-) in XP_638704.1[25]
Antennapedia peptide	RQIKIWFQNRMMKWKK(GG)	In-vitro(Cancer cells) with fusion to p21, In-vivo(mouse) with demonstrated anticancer	0.199(-)

		activity)[26]	
Eosinophil Cationic Protein(ECP 32-41)	RYRWRCKNQN	In-Vitro(BEAS-2B cells) Small peptides[27]	0.110(-)
PACAP(11–38)	SRYRKQMAVKKYLA AVL GKRYKQR VKNK	In-vitro(Fluorophores)[28]	0.144(-)
Arg27-PACAP(11–38)	SRYRKQRAVKKYLA AVL GKRYKQRV KNK	Streptavidin, Id1/3-PA7 peptide and Ribozyme in living cells [28]	0.713(+)
Tp10/Pepfect-3	AGYLLGKINLKALAALAKKIL	Lipid vesicles[29] DNA with N-terminal stearic acid[30]	0.095(-)
Pep-1	KETWWETWTEWSQPKKKRV	Epidermal Growth Factor(EGF)[31]	0.253(-)
PenetraMax	KWFKIQMQIRRWKNKR	Insulin, In-Vivo in mouse as an intranasal mixture[32]	0.280(-) 0.309(-) with C-terminal “GGSG” 0.569(+) with C-terminal “SVAS”
MAP	KLALKLALKALKAALKLA	Induction of apoptosis, Cytotoxic[33]	0.065(-)
HcT(9-32)	LGTYTQDFNKFHTFPQTAIGVGAP	Mouse Macrophages, fused to C-terminus of EGFP[34]	0.062(-)
Hepatitis B virus preS2	PLSSIFSRIGDP	HEK293T cells and Primary mouse bone marrow cells, fused to N-terminus of EGFP[35]	0.141(-)
439A	GPFHFYQFLFPPV	N-terminal fusion to PSIF mediate cytotoxicity in A431, HELA and CHO [36]	0(-)
435B	GSPWGLQHHPRT	N-terminal fusion to PSIF mediate cytotoxicity in A431, HELA and CHO [36]	0.124(-)

Several alternative CPP peptides, like 439A, 435B are more efficient than TAT in mediating the delivery of exogenous proteins into cells. In addition, Several other peptides like the (TCTP)-PTD domain, ECP 32-41 or PACAP(11–38) are derived from human proteins, and are predicted to have minimal, if any, immunogenicity.

The N-terminal fusion of these peptides to Bid, or the C-terminal fusion of HcT(9-32) to a modified Caspase-3, are predicted to produce effective fusion proteins that could enter 100% of the cells within a multicellular organism, and are predicted to confer effective protection of the organism[1] against infection by viruses that encodes the targeted protease, even with inefficient gene delivery that only transfects a minor amount of the cells within said organism.

Conclusions

We performed a comprehensive literature review on Riboviria (RNA viruses, including Reverse-transcribing viruses) and their encoded conserved proteases, the cellular Apoptotic pathway and its activation through a proteolytic cascade, and proposed 3 separate molecules and their engineering strategy to booby-trap the apoptosis pathway for activation upon the intracellular expression of a viral protease.

Lastly, we discussed the methods of delivery of such proteins into a patient or any multicellular organism, with specific constraints on the Protein-Transduction domains (PTD) which is required to be both secretable using the Mammalian secretion pathway, and to be able to efficiently transduce most cell types within a mammalian host, both of which are necessary for a gene therapy based approach to produce sterilizing immunity against a specific RNA viral family.

Our approach have a unique advantage when compared to both conventional antiviral drugs and DRACOs: By targeting a specific signature of a viral family (protease activity) that is both highly conserved within the family and is not found in a normal human cell, this approach is highly resistant to viral mutation that may confer resistance to ordinary inhibitor-based therapeutics (the virus need to mutate the Protease active site and all the proteolytic cleavage sites processed by said protease, simultaneously, in order to escape such an approach), while in the same time being much safer when compared to another broad-spectrum antiviral therapeutic option, the dsRNA-activated caspase Oligomerizer (DRACO)[1], which is potentially an antineoplastic agent as many long double-stranded RNA species resides within the nucleus, which can erroneously activate the DRACO response during cellular mitosis[39], as it naturally activates the Protein Kinase R (PKR) pathway, the basis of the DRACO system.

REFERENCES

- [1] Rider TH, Zook CE, Boettcher TL, Wick ST, Pancoast JS, Zusman BD. Broad-spectrum antiviral therapeutics. *PLoS One*. 2011;6(7):e22572. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0022572. Epub 2011 Jul 27. PMID: 21818340; PMCID: PMC3144912.
- [2] Rodamilans B, Shan H, Pasin F, García JA. Plant Viral Proteases: Beyond the Role of Peptide Cutters. *Front Plant Sci*. 2018 May 17;9:666. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2018.00666. PMID: 29868107; PMCID: PMC5967125.
- [3] Wolf YI, Kazlauskas D, Iranzo J, Lucía-Sanz A, Kuhn JH, Krupovic M, Dolja VV, Koonin EV. Origins and Evolution of the Global RNA Virome. *mBio*. 2018 Nov 27;9(6):e02329-18. doi: 10.1128/mBio.02329-18. PMID: 30482837; PMCID: PMC6282212.
- [4] Hulo C, de Castro E, Masson P, Bougueleret L, Bairoch A, Xenarios I, Le Mercier P. ViralZone: a knowledge resource to understand virus diversity. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2011 Jan;39(Database

issue):D576-82. doi: 10.1093/nar/gkq901. Epub 2010 Oct 14. PMID: 20947564; PMCID: PMC3013774.

[5] Fernández-Correa I, Truchado DA, Gomez-Lucia E, Doménech A, Pérez-Tris J, Schmidt-Chanasit J, Cadar D, Benítez L. A novel group of avian astroviruses from Neotropical passerine birds broaden the diversity and host range of Astroviridae. *Sci Rep.* 2019 Jul 2;9(1):9513. doi: 10.1038/s41598-019-45889-3. PMID: 31266971; PMCID: PMC6606752.

[6] Yokoyama M, Oka T, Takagi H, Kojima H, Okabe T, Nagano T, Tohya Y, Sato H. A Proposal for a Structural Model of the Feline Calicivirus Protease Bound to the Substrate Peptide under Physiological Conditions. *Front Microbiol.* 2017 Jul 25;8:1383. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2017.01383. PMID: 28790989; PMCID: PMC5524728.

[7] Posthuma CC, Te Velthuis AJW, Snijder EJ. Nidovirus RNA polymerases: Complex enzymes handling exceptional RNA genomes. *Virus Res.* 2017 Apr 15;234:58-73. doi: 10.1016/j.virusres.2017.01.023. Epub 2017 Feb 6. PMID: 28174054; PMCID: PMC7114556.

[8]

<https://www.bio-rad.com/en-us/prime-pcr-assays/pathway/apoptosis-survival-caspase-cascade>

[9] Vocero-Akbani AM, Heyden NV, Lissy NA, Ratner L, Dowdy SF. Killing HIV-infected cells by transduction with an HIV protease-activated caspase-3 protein. *Nat Med.* 1999 Jan;5(1):29-33. doi: 10.1038/4710. PMID: 9883836.

[10] Smart AD, Pache RA, Thomsen ND, Kortemme T, Davis GW, Wells JA. Engineering a light-activated caspase-3 for precise ablation of neurons in vivo. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2017 Sep 26;114(39):E8174-E8183. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1705064114. Epub 2017 Sep 11. PMID: 28893998; PMCID: PMC5625904.

[11] Wagner HJ, Weber W. Design of a Human Rhinovirus-14 3C Protease-Inducible Caspase-3. *Molecules.* 2019 May 21;24(10):1945. doi: 10.3390/molecules24101945. PMID: 31117169; PMCID: PMC6571611.

[12] [Crooks GE](#), [Hon G](#), [Chandonia JM](#), [Brenner SE](#) WebLogo: A sequence logo generator, *Genome Research*, 14:1188-1190, (2004)

[13] Fischer U, Stroh C, Schulze-Osthoff K. Unique and overlapping substrate specificities of caspase-8 and caspase-10. *Oncogene.* 2006 Jan 5;25(1):152-9. doi: 10.1038/sj.onc.1209015. PMID: 16186808.

[14] Riddle-Taylor E, Nagasaki K, Lopez J, Esquivel CO, Martinez OM, Krams SM. Mutations to bid cleavage sites protect hepatocytes from apoptosis after ischemia/reperfusion injury. *Transplantation.* 2007 Sep 27;84(6):778-85. doi: 10.1097/01.tp.0000281555.18782.2b. PMID: 17893612; PMCID: PMC4084732.

[15] Orzechowska, E.J., Kozłowska, E., Czuby, A. *et al.* Controlled delivery of BID protein fused with TAT peptide sensitizes cancer cells to apoptosis. *BMC Cancer* **14**, 771 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2407-14-771>

[16] T Tenev, M Marani, I McNeish and NR Lemoine

Pro-caspase-3 overexpression sensitises ovarian cancer cells to proteasome inhibitors

[17] Sutton VR, Davis JE, Cancilla M, Johnstone RW, Ruefli AA, Sedelies K, Browne KA, Trapani JA. Initiation of apoptosis by granzyme B requires direct cleavage of bid, but not direct granzyme B-mediated caspase activation. *J Exp Med.* 2000 Nov 20;192(10):1403-14. doi: 10.1084/jem.192.10.1403. PMID: 11085743; PMCID: PMC2193191.

[18] Wei MC, Lindsten T, Mootha VK, Weiler S, Gross A, Ashiya M, Thompson CB, Korsmeyer SJ. tBID, a membrane-targeted death ligand, oligomerizes BAK to release cytochrome c. *Genes Dev.*

2000 Aug 15;14(16):2060-71. PMID: 10950869; PMCID: PMC316859.

[19] Korsmeyer, S., Wei, M., Saito, M. et al. Pro-apoptotic cascade activates BID, which oligomerizes BAK or BAX into pores that result in the release of cytochrome c. *Cell Death Differ* 7, 1166–1173 (2000). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.cdd.4400783>

[20] Hsu EC, Hsi B, Hirota-Tsuchihara M, Ruland J, Iorio C, Sarangi F, Diao J, Migliaccio G, Tyrrell DL, Kneteman N, Richardson CD. Modified apoptotic molecule (BID) reduces hepatitis C virus infection in mice with chimeric human livers. *Nat Biotechnol*. 2003 May;21(5):519-25. doi: 10.1038/nbt817. Epub 2003 Apr 21. PMID: 12704395.

[21] Flinterman M, Farzaneh F, Habib N, Malik F, Gäken J, Tavassoli M. Delivery of therapeutic proteins as secretable TAT fusion products. *Mol Ther*. 2009 Feb;17(2):334-42. doi: 10.1038/mt.2008.256. Epub 2008 Dec 2. PMID: 19050698; PMCID: PMC2835060.

[22] Duckert P, Brunak S, Blom N. Prediction of proprotein convertase cleavage sites. *Protein Eng Des Sel*. 2004 Jan;17(1):107-12. doi: 10.1093/protein/gzh013. PMID: 14985543.

[23] Moonhee Kim, Miyoung Kim, Hyo Young Kim, Sol Kim, Jaehoon Jung, Jeehye Maeng, Jun Chang, Kyunglim Lee,

A protein transduction domain located at the NH₂-terminus of human translationally controlled tumor protein for delivery of active molecules to cells,

Biomaterials,

Volume 32, Issue 1,

2011,

Pages 222-230,

ISSN 0142-9612,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2010.08.077>.

[24] Kim M, Maeng J, Jung J, Kim HY, Kim HJ, Kwon Y, Lee K. Design and evaluation of variants of the protein transduction domain originated from translationally controlled tumor protein. *Eur J Pharm Sci*. 2011 May 18;43(1-2):25-31. doi: 10.1016/j.ejps.2011.03.007. Epub 2011 Apr 2. PMID: 21440624.

[26] Kousparou, C.A., Yiacoymi, E., Deonarain, M.P. et al. Generation of a selectively cytotoxic fusion protein against p53 mutated cancers. *BMC Cancer* 12, 338 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2407-12-338>

[27] Fang SL, Fan TC, Fu HW, Chen CJ, Hwang CS, Hung TJ, Lin LY, Chang MD. A novel cell-penetrating peptide derived from human eosinophil cationic protein. *PLoS One*. 2013;8(3):e57318. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0057318. Epub 2013 Mar 4. PMID: 23469189; PMCID: PMC3587609.

[28] Doan ND, Létourneau M, Vaudry D, Doucet N, Folch B, Vaudry H, Fournier A, Chatenet D. Design and characterization of novel cell-penetrating peptides from pituitary adenylate cyclase-activating polypeptide. *J Control Release*. 2012 Oct 28;163(2):256-65. doi: 10.1016/j.jconrel.2012.08.021. Epub 2012 Aug 24. PMID: 22922050.

[29] Yandek LE, Pokorny A, Florén A, Knoelke K, Langel U, Almeida PF. Mechanism of the cell-penetrating peptide transportan 10 permeation of lipid bilayers. *Biophys J*. 2007 Apr 1;92(7):2434-44. doi: 10.1529/biophysj.106.100198. Epub 2007 Jan 11. PMID: 17218466; PMCID: PMC1864827.

[30] Lehto T, Simonson OE, Mäger I, Ezzat K, Sork H, Copolovici DM, Viola JR, Zaghoul EM, Lundin P, Moreno PM, Mäe M, Oskolkov N, Suhorutšenko J, Smith CI, Andaloussi SE. A peptide-based

- vector for efficient gene transfer in vitro and in vivo. *Mol Ther.* 2011 Aug;19(8):1457-67. doi: 10.1038/mt.2011.10. Epub 2011 Feb 22. PMID: 21343913; PMCID: PMC3149163.
- [31] Luo XG, Ma DY, Wang Y, Li W, Wang CX, He YY, Gu XC, Li XM, Zhou H, Zhang TC. Fusion with pep-1, a cell-penetrating peptide, enhances the transmembrane ability of human epidermal growth factor. *Biosci Biotechnol Biochem.* 2016;80(3):584-90. doi: 10.1080/09168451.2015.1091714. Epub 2015 Oct 7. PMID: 26442995.
- [32] Khafagy el-S, Kamei N, Nielsen EJ, Nishio R, Takeda-Morishita M. One-month subchronic toxicity study of cell-penetrating peptides for insulin nasal delivery in rats. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* 2013 Nov;85(3 Pt A):736-43. doi: 10.1016/j.ejpb.2013.09.014. Epub 2013 Sep 21. PMID: 24060698.
- [33] Qiu, Y., Yu, Q., Shi, K. et al. Cell-penetrating peptides induce apoptosis and necrosis through specific mechanism and cause impairment of Na⁺-K⁺-ATPase and mitochondria. *Amino Acids* 49, 75–88 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-016-2327-8>
- [34] Ma J, Xu J, Guan L, Hu T, Liu Q, Xiao J, Zhang Y. Cell-penetrating peptides mediated protein cross-membrane delivery and its use in bacterial vector vaccine. *Fish Shellfish Immunol.* 2014 Jul;39(1):8-16. doi: 10.1016/j.fsi.2014.04.003. Epub 2014 Apr 16. PMID: 24746937.
- [35] Oess S, Hildt E. Novel cell permeable motif derived from the PreS2-domain of hepatitis-B virus surface antigens. *Gene Ther.* 2000 May;7(9):750-8. doi: 10.1038/sj.gt.3301154. PMID: 10822301.
- [36] Kamada H, Okamoto T, Kawamura M, Shibata H, Abe Y, Ohkawa A, Nomura T, Sato M, Mukai Y, Sugita T, Imai S, Nagano K, Tsutsumi Y, Nakagawa S, Mayumi T, Tsunoda S. Creation of novel cell-penetrating peptides for intracellular drug delivery using systematic phage display technology originated from Tat transduction domain. *Biol Pharm Bull.* 2007 Feb;30(2):218-23. doi: 10.1248/bpb.30.218. PMID: 17268054.
- [37] Hu Y, Ding L, Spencer DM, Núñez G. WD-40 repeat region regulates Apaf-1 self-association and procaspase-9 activation. *J Biol Chem.* 1998 Dec 11;273(50):33489-94. doi: 10.1074/jbc.273.50.33489. PMID: 9837928.
- [38] Lauber K, Appel HA, Schlosser SF, Gregor M, Schulze-Osthoff K, Wesselborg S. The adapter protein apoptotic protease-activating factor-1 (Apaf-1) is proteolytically processed during apoptosis. *J Biol Chem.* 2001 Aug 10;276(32):29772-81. doi: 10.1074/jbc.M101524200. Epub 2001 May 31. PMID: 11387322.
- [39] Yoosik Kim, Jung Hyun Lee, Jong-Eun Park, Jun Cho, Hyerim Yi, and V. Narry Kim (2014). PKR is activated by cellular dsRNAs during mitosis and acts as a mitotic regulator. *Genes & Development* 28: 1310-1322. DOI: [10.1101/gad.242644.114](https://doi.org/10.1101/gad.242644.114) Genes & Dev. 2014. 28: 1310-1322